

Usability and Performance Assessment of Semiautonomous Hand-Wrist Prosthetic Control

1stGianmarco Cirelli
CREO Lab, UCBM
Rome, Italy
gianmarco.cirelli@unicampus.it

2ndChristian Tamantini
ISTC, CNR
Rome, Italy
christian.tamantini@cnr.it

3rdEnrica Stefanelli
CREO Lab, UCBM
Rome, Italy
e.stefanelli@unicampus.it

4thRoberto Billardello
CREO Lab, UCBM
Rome, Italy
r.billardello@unicampus.it

5thLoredana Zollo
CREO Lab, UCBM
Rome, Italy
l.zollo@unicampus.it

6thLuigi Pietro Cordella
UNINA
Naples, Italy
cordel@unina.it

7thFrancesca Cordella
CREO Lab, UCBM
Rome, Italy
f.cordella@unicampus.it

Abstract—Semiautonomous control strategies (SCS) could significantly enhance the reliability and naturalness of prosthetic hand control. Integrating a Computer Vision System (CVS) endows the prosthetic hand with the ability to recognize objects and autonomously select the most suitable hand gesture configuration, while maintaining the user in the loop.

In this paper, a SCS combining electromyographic (EMG) signals with a CVS is presented. The system was tested on three able-bodied participants during Pick & Place tasks, achieving a 100% success rate, a mean usability score above 82/100, and a low cognitive burden with an average "Mental Demand" of 31.65/100.

Index Terms—Upper Limb Prosthesis, Computer Vision, Semiautonomous control

I. INTRODUCTION

The loss of an upper limb significantly impacts quality of life, and current prostheses, relying solely on electromyographic (EMG) signals, face limitations in adaptability and control. Threshold EMG control is sequential and unintuitive, allowing few hand gestures to be managed, while muscle pattern recognition remains unreliable [1], impacting system usability and increasing prosthesis use abandonment. Semiautonomous control strategies (SCS) leveraging Computer Vision Systems (CVS) have been proposed to reduce cognitive load and improve the accuracy, naturalness, and intuitiveness of prosthetic control.

The approaches proposed in literature are based on the combined use of RGB camera and ultrasonic sensors to classify hand gestures and estimate wrist orientation [2], or on the adoption of RGB-D cameras [3], but their size and weight limits their integration into prostheses. To enhance grasp selection and reduce computational costs, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) were employed for RGB image classification [4], but relinquishing the estimate of the wrist orientation.

This work is funded by the European Union - Next Generation EU - NRRP M4.C2 - Investment 1.5 Establishing and strengthening of Innovation Ecosystems for sustainability (Project n. ECS00000024 Rome Technopole) and by the INAIL Prosthetic Center with the NoProblem Project (CUP: E57G23000270005).

The aim of this work is to introduce a novel SCS, which simultaneously considers the user's motion intention and handles both hand and wrist configuration [5]. Unlike previous methods, in which the system independently selected the hand gesture, this approach allows the user to intentionally choose the grasp, while the vision system adjusts the orientation of the wrist and suggests potential corrections. Moreover, the SCS was integrated in a commercial hand-wrist prosthesis, and it was validated in terms of performance and usability of the integrated system in a real-world context with able-body users.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

An overview of the proposed approach and of the integrated system is shown in Figure 1. This work builds upon previous research [5] and has been integrated into a real robotic system.

Fig. 1. Block Diagram of the System.

The SCS combines information from the CVS and the user intention module to optimize grasp execution and wrist orientation in a prosthetic hand. Indeed, it processes an RGB image of the environment, captured by the prosthesis-embedded camera, and the user's intent, detected by an EMG classifier, interpreting the desired hand gesture. By combining these inputs, it effectively manages both coherent and non-coherent scenarios, accurately determining wrist orientation to optimize hand reshaping. The approach involves three sequential steps: Object Detection, Grasp Selection, and Orientation Estimation.

Visual feedback is provided to the user through two colored LEDs, which indicate whether an object is detected (green one) and if there is any discrepancy between the detected object and the EMG classifier output (red one).

The algorithm uses four macro-categories (Lateral, Pinch, Pointing, Power) from the EMG classifier to assign configurations tailored to specific objects. In this way, the EMG classifier maintains high classification accuracy by limiting the number of considered classes, while simultaneously enhancing the prosthesis grasping capabilities. This strategy handles 13 gestures: rest, open hand, medium wrap, fixed hook, adducted thumb, lateral, pointing, 2-digit pinch, 3-digit pinch, spherical, parallel extension pronation, supination.

The CVS is composed by a Single Board Computer (SBC), i.e. the Raspberry Pi 4B with 8GB RAM as computing power, and a 16MP Camera with capability of automatically regulating focus. The SBC desktop is remotely controlled via virtual network computing and a power bank was used as an energy supply (5V DC and 3A via a USB-C port) to make the system portable.

User motion intention is retrieved by a Non-Linear Regression (NLR) Classifier [6], which exploited raw sEMG signals collected from six 13E200 Myobock Electrode (Ottobock) through a NI USB-6002 DAQ (sampling frequency: 1 kHz). Input data were segmented in time windows of 200ms with a 50ms overlap (prediction time = 150 ms). Majority voting scheme was applied to determine the final predicted gesture.

The commercial hand-wrist prosthetic device is composed by the Touch Bionics (Össur) RoboLimb hand and the Electric wrist rotator (Ottobock).

To evaluate the performance and the usability of the system, 3 able bodied volunteers (27.0 ± 2.65 mean age) were asked to execute 3 times each of the 13 Pick & Place tasks previously listed, wearing the prosthetic device endowed with the developed SCS. Success Rate (SR) [%] in task execution, and Time to Accomplish the Task (TAT) [s] were computed for each macro-category of grasp. Specifically, the task was successfully completed considering a maximum of 3 attempts. Lastly, the system usability and the overall workload experienced by the user were assessed using the System Usability Scale (SUS) and the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) computed in the range 0-100.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed SCS showed a mean frequency of execution of $2.07 \pm 0.15 FPS$ and an accuracy in grasp classification of 99.80% [5]. Figure 2 shows the results of TAT, SUS score and NASA TLX, obtained from 3 able-bodied participants.

The SR= 100% for all the participant involved, demonstrating an excellent capability to utilize the integrated system. Moreover, the results obtained from the three participants highlight an excellent usability of the system, with an average SUS score of 82.5 ± 6.61 , i.e higher than 80.3 (Grade A), as well as a low perceived cognitive load, with an average "Mental Demand" percentage in NASA TLX of 31.65 ± 12.58 .

Fig. 2. Boxplot of TAT evaluated for each macro-category of grasp (A); SUS score obtained for each participants (B); outcomes of NASA TLX (C)

In addition, the mean TAT for each macro-category of grasp was $10.69 \pm 5.47s$ for *Power*, $12.73 \pm 6.39s$ for *Pointing*, $12.64 \pm 6.29s$ for *Lateral*, $13.02 \pm 7.04s$ for *Pinch*. The current results align with expectations for a healthy subject, although the initial image processing takes $2.41s$ on average to activate prosthesis control. However, it is challenging to provide an objective assessment without comparing it to results from other types of control strategies, especially with a pure EMG control strategy.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a preliminary evaluation of the usability and perception of the SCS proposed in our previous work. Despite the promising outcomes, future steps will be devoted to test the SCS on a larger population and compare it with a pure EMG-based control approach, to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach in improving the control of the prosthetic device and in reducing the cognitive load on the user.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Yadav and K. Veer, "Recent trends and challenges of surface electromyography in prosthetic applications," *Biomedical Engineering Letters*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 353–373, 2023.
- [2] S. Došen, C. Cipriani, M. Kostić, M. Controzzi, M. C. Carozza, and D. B. Popović, "Cognitive vision system for control of dexterous prosthetic hands: experimental evaluation," *Journal of neuroengineering and rehabilitation*, vol. 7, pp. 1–14, 2010.
- [3] M. N. Castro and S. Dosen, "Continuous semi-autonomous prosthesis control using a depth sensor on the hand," *Frontiers in Neurobotics*, 2022.
- [4] M. C. F. Castro, W. C. Pinheiro, and G. Rigolin, "A hybrid 3d printed hand prosthesis prototype based on semg and a fully embedded computer vision system," *Frontiers in Neurobotics*, vol. 15, p. 751282, 2022.
- [5] G. Cirelli, C. Tamantini, L. P. Cordella, and F. Cordella, "A semiautonomous control strategy based on computer vision for a hand-wrist prosthesis," *Robotics*, vol. 12, no. 6, p. 152, 2023.
- [6] F. Leone, F. Mereu, C. Gentile, F. Cordella, E. Gruppioni, and L. Zollo, "Hierarchical strategy for semg classification of the hand/wrist gestures and forces of transradial amputees," *Frontiers in Neurobotics*, vol. 17, p. 1092006, 03 2023.